

A STUDY ON THE TRANSLATION OF EPITHETS

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Abstract: This article explores the role of translating epithets in Uzbek and English. It examines key aspects of translation and highlights essential elements of cultural communication involved in the process. The aim is to investigate the significance of accurately translating epithets and to analyze their impact in two linguistically and culturally distinct languages.

Keywords: literal meaning, adaptation, localization, figurative meaning.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o‘zbek va ingliz tillarida epitetlarni tarjima qilishning ahamiyati, tarjima jarayonida ishtirok etadigan madaniy muloqotning muhim elementlari tahlil qiladi, shuningdek epitetlarni muqobil tarjima qilishning ahamiyati, til va madaniy jihatdan bir-biridan farq qiladigan ikki tilda bunday tarjimaning ta’siri o‘rganiladi

Kalit so‘zlar: asl ma’no, moslashish, lokalizatsiya, ko‘chma ma’no.

Introduction

In today’s globalized world understanding other culture and literature has become more common and in this case translation plays an important role. In general, translation refers to the conversion of a text from one language into another. Nowadays, it is employed as a form of communication, as well as an effective mode of learning and applying what has been learned.

Improving the quality of translations in Uzbek literature, as well as translating works from English literature, has become a critical task for both linguists and translators. Literature and poetry use vivid, innovative words and expressions that go beyond their literal meaning to portray ideas in creative or emotionally strong ways. In the context, epithets endowed with vivid pragmatic features that greatly impact the addressability of a literary work should be the focus of current research. The inner predicativity of an epithet, derived from its attributive nature, along with the author’s unique creative style, makes this trope into an important means of expressing addressee-oriented semantics in a literary text.

Cultural knowledge, including understanding of diverse subcultures and the like, is regarded as an essential component of producing high quality translations. Readers consider translated writings as understandable and relevant when they use cultural nuances and various language techniques correctly [1]. A translator is regarded as an active agent in making decisions about the axiological dimensions of a literary work and how it may be situated in a particular tradition [2]

Epithets are regarded as one of the key devices for showing expressiveness and emotional impact in a text, owing to their figurative and evaluative-axiological functions. Numerous studies in both literary criticism and linguistics have explored this stylistic element, including the works of Manieva (2007) [3], Gubanov (2009) [4], Lyubovskaya (2016) [5], among others.

According to Zhen (2004), an English transferred epithet consists of a transferred modifier and a central word. Its formation is influenced by contextual presupposition, which governs the semantic shift and restructuring. A defining characteristic of the transferred epithet is the semantic tension between the modifier and the head word. In this regard, adjectives play a central role, as they are used to investigate various transferred forms, the mechanisms of semantic reinterpretation, and strategies for translation [6]. Similarly, Bulakhova (2017), in her article on epithets, analyzes and systematizes a range of definitions of the phenomenon, offering a comprehensive classification that synthesizes available material and data. She also identifies structural models of epithets based on their central or peripheral positions within the overall system. Furthermore, the study emphasizes two essential

conditions for identifying an epithet: the presence of attributive relations within a collocation, and the stylistic markedness (non-neutrality) of its determinative component [7].

Methods

This study examines the use and translation of epithets in Abdulhamid Chulpan’s novel *Night and Day* [8]. The accurate rendering of epithets is crucial, as it requires maintaining the author’s intended meaning and stylistic function through the selection of precise semantic equivalents and ensuring pragmatic consistency in the target language. Achieving stylistic fidelity depends on carefully choosing corresponding linguistic units, which necessitates a thorough pre-translation analysis of the literary and cultural conventions of the target readership.

Using a linguo-stylistic approach within a comparative framework, the research uncovers semantic, pragmatic, and stylistic nuances in both the source and translated texts. It further highlights the decisive role of context in shaping these subtleties and in conveying the cultural and historical uniqueness of the original work. In essence, this method proves essential for exploring the interplay between language form, cultural background, and stylistic function in communication. Its application is particularly valuable in translation studies, literary criticism, and cross-cultural linguistics, where style contributes meaning beyond the literal text.

Results and discussion

The accurate interpretation of epithets is a critical aspect of translation, as misrepresentation can significantly distort meaning. This arises because the formation and perception of epithets differ greatly across languages. Words, gestures, expressions, or signs may carry contrasting connotations: positive in one language yet negative in another, sometimes even conflicting with cultural norms of etiquette. For instance, in a text where an epithet describes a character pointing with an index finger, the translator must carefully examine its significance in both the source and target cultures before rendering it.

According to Kotov.A.A., Mukhina.E. A. (2021), fixed epithets, characteristic of all folklore genres, form an important part of the spiritual hymn, as they serve as the primary means of expressing the normative evaluation of works of oral folk creativity, where the subject is the folklore community and the object is the external world [9].

Adaptation and localization serve as crucial strategies that facilitate cross-cultural communication. Localization means to modifying epithets so they resonate meaningfully with the target audience, while adaptation involves contextual adjustments that alter specific epithets or scenarios without undermining the intended purpose. Since each language has its own norms, a literal translation of epithets often fails to convey the intended nuance and may even be rejected by readers from a different cultural background.

The expressive power of an epithet stems from its intentional nature: shaped by a creative process where both the author and the reader are active participants in a conscious and purposeful act. This process ensures that a fact or event is etched in the reader’s mind as a crafted impression. Epithets thus play a crucial role in conveying the writer’s communicative purpose. That’s why in the works of renowned Uzbek writer Chulpan, we often encounter numerous extended epithets and a rich blending of epithets with other figurative devices within single expressions.

Conclusion

Translators must demonstrate strong cultural awareness, tailoring their work to the worldview and conceptual frameworks of the target audience. This includes adjusting idiomatic expressions, humor, figurative language, and other stylistic elements, while also localizing practical details such as time references, currency, measurements, names, colours, etiquette rules, and writing conventions.

Such strategies ensure that the translated epithets remain faithful to the original while being accessible, engaging, and meaningful to its readers. Ultimately, this approach not only preserves the essence of the source material but also enhances its effectiveness and relevance for the target culture.

Epithets play a significant role in today's imaginative fiction as decorative elements that can convey the author's attitude toward the character, idea, and general plot. The translator must choose words carefully so that they have the same denotative and connotative meanings in order to convey the author's goal.

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